

tomonlama o'rgangan ma'qul. Ya'ni, berilayotgan bilim miqdori emas, uni o'zlashtirish, amaliy qo'llay olish ahamiyatga ega .

Xulosa qilib shuni aytish mumkinki, ko'zlangan maqsadga, yaxshi natijaga erishish uchun avvalo o'qituvchi o'z fanini yaxshi bilishi, ilg'or zamonaviy o'qitish usullaridan xabardor bo'lishi va ulardan samarali foydalanish yo'llarini kashf eta olishi kerak. Shundagina o'qitish sifati ham, talabalarda fanni o'zlashtirish darajasi ham yuqori bo'ladi. *“ Ta'lim jarayoniga ilg'or pedagogik texnologiyani tadbiq etish kadrlar tayorlashga yo'naltirilgan umumiy jarayon mazmuninig sifat jihatdan o'zgarishini ta'minlaydi”* [2. T. Hamidova, 582-bet]. O'quvchilarga eng zarur, eng muhim narsalarnigina o'rgatish kerak-ki, u bir umrga eslab qolsin. Doim fan orqali, iloji bo'lsa har tomonlama o'quvchining ongiga ta'sir qilish, uni uyg'otish, bilimni uquvga aylantirish va o'quvchini doim mashg'ul bo'lishga majbur qilish kerak. O'qituvchi shunday izlansinki, dars o'quvchi uchun ixtiyoriy mashg'ulotga aylansin.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

1. Janikova, Vera; Michels-McGovers, Monika. Aspekte des Hochschulfachs: Methodik und Didaktik des Unterrichts Deutsch als Fremdsprache im Überblick. T. 2. Hamidova, “Agrar sohada nemis tili darslarini samarali tashkil etish usullari” Jamiyat va innovatsiyalar. Jurnal 7mart, 2021 yil
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INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES AND COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract: The main purpose of scientific, scientific-technical and innovative activities is to obtain new scientific knowledge through research and development and their focus on the creation and introduction of new competitive technologies, types of equipment, materials, etc. to ensure the innovative development of society and training of innovative specialists.

Key words: ICT, modernizing, OECD, global.

The concept of pedagogical education development among the key tasks defines the training of teachers–researchers for all components of education (preschool, complete general secondary, alternative, specialized, professional (vocational) and special pre-higher, higher, including postgraduate), who are able to solve complex problems in the field of pedagogical and/or research activities, which involves a deep rethinking of existing and creating new holistic knowledge and/or professional practice⁶⁹. The main purpose of scientific, scientific-technical and innovative activities is to obtain new scientific knowledge through research and development and their focus on the creation and introduction of new competitive technologies, types of equipment, materials, etc. to ensure the innovative development of society and training of innovative specialists.

⁶⁹ Zhu, S., Hao, Y. H., Xu, S., & MacLeod, J. (2020). Understanding social media competence in higher education: Development and validation of an instrument. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 57(8), 1935–1955. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0735633118820631>

The priority tasks of the university in the field of scientific, scientific and technical activities:

1. The development of fundamental research in the field of natural, humanitarian, psychological and pedagogical, socio-economic sciences with the aim of their further use for the development of priority areas of science and technology, social development and the development of the country's economy⁷⁰. Performing applied research and development in order to effectively use and develop scientific potential, attracting additional funds to solve social and other problems of the industry. Research and development of theoretical and methodological foundations for the establishment and development of higher education, strengthening the influence of science on solving the problems of education and upbringing, preserving and strengthening the defining character of science in the development of society, culture and economy.

The support for existing scientific schools and the establishment of new ones. The implementation of activities to support the scientific research of young scientists and gifted students, their involvement in scientific schools, etc. The life-long education programme identifies priorities and epochs of the future: Rapid communication, a planetary economy, increased competition and an increase in the number of older people and low-skilled workers, modernizing the types and forms of knowledge areas and professions⁷¹, combining large and small; understanding and applying capabilities of the brain; expanding the scope of services, including educational ones; awareness of the need for self-learning, self-improvement and self-development.

The main indicator for identifying basic competencies is the business sector and employers. OECD has implemented the Definition and Selection of Competencies project to determine the competencies that are relevant at the present

⁷⁰ Wang, N., Young, T., Wilhite, S. C., & Marczyk, G. (2011). Assessing students' emotional competence in higher education: Development and validation of the widener emotional learning scale. *Journal of Psychoeducational Assessment*, 29(1), 47–62. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734282909359394>

⁷¹ Mengual-Andrés, S., Roig-Vila, R., & Mira, J. B. (2016). Delphi study for the design and validation of a questionnaire about digital competences in higher education. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 13(1), 12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-016-0009-y>

stage of society's development and that will be in demand in the future⁷². The results of the study are used by interested national governments and global educational systems, since the latest state development programmes define human capital as a priority for overcoming deficiencies and giving the educational process a modern practical significance. OECD defines key (universal or global) competencies that contribute to the effective work of specialists in various professional and/or social spheres and to the qualitative self-realization of individuals and the life of society as a whole.

Abbas finds a need to include ICT impact in Shulham's definition of curricular knowledge. He argues that teachers must have proper knowledge of ICT so that they can adapt the ICT tools to meet the needs of their lessons. He also shows his concern when he finds that Cuban have highlighted a serious deficiency of ICT integration despite increasing number of technologies⁷³. He attributes this drawback to irrelevant or insufficient teacher-training programs for pre-service teachers. His research asks for well-designed and technology-oriented teacher training programs. His research concluded that teacher preparation programs need to meet the needs and demands of the future and this is likely to strengthen the link between technology integration and educational reforms.

It was stated that thanks to the use of online and other technologies, future teachers can more effectively acquire knowledge, skills and abilities in many other areas. It was asserted that in modern conditions, pedagogical and scientific-pedagogical workers need to overcome the highly specialized line of the learning process. To develop this area, it is necessary to intensify interdisciplinary and transborder cooperation, as well as to develop inclusive and innovative approaches to learning and teaching⁷⁴. The results are explained by significant transformational

⁷² López-Bonilla, J. M., & López-Bonilla, L. M. (2014). Holistic competence approach in tourism higher education: An exploratory study in Spain. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 17(4), 312–326. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500.2012.720248>

⁷³ Cuban, L. (2001). *Oversold and underused: Computers in the classroom*. London: Harvard University Press. <https://doi.org/10.12691/education-2-9-4> (2004).

⁷⁴ Monar, M. A. C., & Rodríguez, M. C. V. (2020). A philosophical and sociological perspective of environmental professional competence in higher education. *Revista Fuentes*, 22(2), 251–260. <https://doi.org/10.12795/revistafuentes.2020.v22.i2.02>

processes in the life of society, its transition to a new level—a smart society, which requires preparing a person for life in a world of diverse connections—from interaction with the immediate environment to global interaction, intercultural communication using information and communication technologies. The practical implementation of certain tasks depends on the teacher as a carrier of intellectual and innovative potential. The results obtained in the course of the experimental study showed that this problem remains open and requires a solution, which is what the system developed by authors is aimed at.

Fast growing educational technologies call for pre-service and in-service teachers to integrate ICT in teaching and learning. Institutions are developing continuous professional development programs to improve teachers' skills of ICT but still there are certain challenges which need proper planning and improvement strategies. Al-Senaidi, Lin, and Poirot supported the idea that there are two types of barriers: external which relate to lack of time and resources, limited technical support and unattended technical problems and internal which reflect teachers' attitudes such as lack of confidence, conservative attitude and poor knowledge of the benefits of technology⁷⁵. Alev investigated ICT integration and possible challenges faced in pre-service teacher training programs. Some of the major challenges found were poor access to ICT tools, large classrooms, and lack of pedagogical and technical support. His study found class management, technical problems, poor ICT skills of teachers and learners, conservative attitude of the teachers about ICT use as further challenges in successful implementation of ICT.

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⁷⁵ Al-Senaidi, S., Lin, L., & Poirot, J. Barriers to adopting technology for teaching and learning in Oman. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2009.03.015> (2009).

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